

Dismissed, Misdiagnosed, or Overlooked: A Young Black Woman's Perspective on Breast Cancer

Anne Diouf

The George Washington University

When I heard about the new breast cancer screening guidelines from the U.S. Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF) on May 9, 2023, I was ecstatic. The last guidelines detailed recommendations for women starting age 50 to 64 years old to obtain a breast mammography every two years. Earlier in the year, I began working on a project with The Missing Pink Breast Cancer Alliance founder Jasmine Souers. Jasmine is not only a breast cancer survivor; she also received the diagnosis at the young age of 26. Throughout our bi-weekly meetings, I slowly got to learn about Jasmine's family history of breast cancer. Her grandmother Bettie was diagnosed with breast cancer, and experienced two recurrences, with the latest recurrence involving metastatic disease. More than 20 years had passed between her first and most recent breast cancer diagnosis. The difference between the two women is the age at which they were diagnosed. Yes, the new screening guidelines have moved up 10 years since the last guidelines in 2016, but what about the women younger than 40 being dismissed, misdiagnosed, or overlooked?

There is never a right time to get breast cancer but most women are over 50 years old when they are diagnosed. For younger women, getting screened for breast cancer is the last thing on their minds. As a 30-year-old woman myself, working on the project with Jasmine was eye-opening. My family history of breast cancer started with my Aunt Charlotte. Throughout her life she had her symptoms dismissed by healthcare providers because she had fibroids, which she refused to have removed for fear the operation could prevent her from having children in the future. When she received a breast cancer diagnosis in her early 30s, it was already too aggressive. She passed away when I was 12 years old. According to the Cleveland Clinic, breast cancer is more advanced and harder to treat when diagnosed at an earlier age.

For Jasmine, having witnessed her grandmother's fight with breast cancer, she and her mother made sure they were performing breast self-exams and getting screened by a healthcare provider. While fortunately to this day her mother has never been diagnosed with breast cancer, Jasmine was diagnosed at 26 years old. But before the diagnosis, Jasmine, through performing routine breast self-exams discovered a hardness to her breast and saw discharge released from her nipple. The first doctor she visited reported that the mammogram and ultrasound results were normal. Even knowing her family history of breast cancer, the doctor told her she was "too young to have cancer." Months passed and Jasmine's symptoms got worse so she decided to seek a different doctor. The results showed they had found cancerous cells. With the support of her mother and Grandmother Bettie, Jasmine underwent a bilateral mastectomy which is when both breasts are removed. She has been living cancer-free. Her story and many others can be found on themorelifemag.com

Yes, Jasmine and I were ecstatic to hear the new screening recommendations but we also had the thought “But what about the younger women?” According to the Cleveland Clinic, younger women tend to ignore symptoms because they believe they are too young to get cancer and some healthcare providers adopt a “wait and see” approach which can delay diagnoses and result in poorer outcomes. Breast cancer symptoms in younger women are the same as breast cancer in women over 50. Family history plays a big role in the risk of developing breast cancer at a younger age. The new guidelines do not recommend breast cancer screenings for people younger than 40 years old. Still, those with a family history of breast cancer or have a known genetic mutation such as BRCA, TP53, PTEN, STK11, PALB2, or CDH1 should speak to their healthcare provider about getting screened earlier. According to the American Cancer Society, incident rates have been slowly increasing by 0.5% since the mid-2000s. Black women are 40% more likely than white women to die from breast cancer.

In my family, no one has been diagnosed with breast cancer since my Aunt Charlotte but working on this magazine project with Jasmine showed me that I can never ignore the fact that I have a higher chance of getting breast cancer earlier than 40 years old. In addition, because I have gained more knowledge about the programs available to those diagnosed with breast cancer in the United States, I feel that I am more prepared to advocate for myself if I am diagnosed. I have learned that the lack of access to resources contributes to more black women dying from breast cancer compared to white women. For my part, I regularly perform breast self-exams. I have also informed all my healthcare providers of my family history of breast cancer.

<https://www.uspreventiveservicestaskforce.org/uspstf/draft-recommendation/breast-cancer-screening-adults>

<https://www.themorelifemag.com/2023-2024-issue/three-generations-one-fight-a-familys-journey-of-love-strength-and-hope>

<https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/diseases/16805-breast-cancer-in-young-women>

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<https://www.nbcnews.com/news/amp/rcna83355>